

3. DELIVERABLES

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Status	Comments
D1.1	Internal Progress Report 1	WP1	CREAMODITE	R	SEN	31 August 2023	31 August 2023	31 August 2023	APPROVED	
D1.2	Minutes of project boards	WP1	CREAMODITE	R	SEN	31 May 2024		5 June 2024	APPROVED	
D2.1	Collections portfolio ZERO WASTE FASHION	WP2	CREAMODITE	DEM	PU	31 May 2023		30 May 2023	APPROVED	
D2.2	Collections portfolio CIRCULAR FASHION	WP2	UMINHO	DEM	PU	31 May 2023		31 May 2023	APPROVED	
D2.3	Collections portfolio CULTURAL HERITAGE AND SUSTAINABLE FASHION	WP2	UCAMPANIA	DEM	PU	31 May 2023		31 May 2023	APPROVED	
D3.1	Videos for video-mapping, light shows and concept videos for LED walls	WP3	CREAMODITE	DEM	PU	31 July 2023		31 July 2023	APPROVED	
D3.2	Report on the digital strategy design and integration into ZERO WASTE FASHION event	WP3	CREAMODITE	R	SEN	31 August 2023	31 August 2023	27 August 2023	APPROVED	
D3.3	Report on the digital strategy design and integration into CIRCULAR FASHION event	WP3	UMINHO	R	SEN	31 August 2023		27 August 2023	APPROVED	
D3.4	Report on the digital strategy design and integration	WP3	UCAMPANIA	DEC	SEN	31 August 2023		27 August 2023	APPROVED	

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	into CULTURAL HERITAGE AND SUSTAINABLE FASHION event									
D4.1	Plan for the event story telling and contents of the show. Choreographic design	WP4	CREAMODITE	R	SEN	30 June 2023		6 July 2023	APPROVED	
D4.2	Public Survey/ questionnaire. Report on the events performance.	WP4	CREAMODITE	R	PU	31 August 2023		31 August 2023	APPROVED	
D4.3	Presentations/contents to be discussed in the roundtables	WP4	CREAMODITE	DEM	PU	30 June 2023		21 June 2023	APPROVED	
D4.4	Fashion film	WP4	CREAMODITE	DEM	PU	31 March 2024		29 May 2024	APPROVED	
D5.1	Project evaluation report	WP5	CREAMODITE	R	SEN	31 May 2024		3 June 2024	APPROVED	
D5.2	Best Practice guide for Sustainable Fashion	WP5	CREAMODITE	R	PU	31 May 2024		29 May 2024	APPROVED	
D5.3	Best Practice guide for impact generation through artistic events	WP5	CREAMODITE	R	PU	31 May 2024		29 May 2024	APPROVED	
D6.1	Communications and Dissemination Plan	WP6	CREAMODITE	R	SEN	30 November 2022		30 November 2022	APPROVED	
D6.2	Evaluation report	WP6	CREAMODITE	R	SEN	31 May 2024		4 June 2024	APPROVED	
D6.3	Kick Off meeting minutes	WP6	CREAMODITE	R	SEN	31 August 2022		22 November 2022	APPROVED	
D6.4	Project website and social media	WP6	Xsentrikarts	DEC	PU	30 November 2022		30 November 2022	APPROVED	